

Project INNOHYPPY Innovative catalyst and its regeneration for clean hydrogen production via methane pyrolysis

Deliverable D 4.3: Report on the electrochemical response of the electrochemical test structure

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This deliverable report covers the carbon powders, by-products obtained after pyrolysis, for electrochemical sensing applications. The deliverable includes: 1) a list of the powders, 2) preparation of carbon-based suspensions for screen printing, 3) preparation of carbon thick films on alumina substrates and their electrochemical characterization, 4) design of the electrochemical sensor test structure, development of a procedure for preparing working (WE), counter (CE), and reference (RE) electrodes and interconnections on the alumina substrate, and 5) demonstration of the electrochemical response of the carbon-based WE in a selected analyte, namely the pesticide imidacloprid (IMD).

1. Carbon-based powders

The powders were received from the partner Institute of Solid State Physics (ISSP), Latvija. JSI investigated carbon powders listed in Table 1, which were formed after pyrolysis as by-products. The powders were derived from different type of catalyst, and different pyrolysis conditions. All the powders were dark, almost black coloured, with a sub-micrometer-sized particles.

Table 1: Carbon-based powders

Powder	Catalyst	Pyrolysis temp [°C]
TP_47	FeNi_7	700
TP_42	FeNi_7	700
TP_43	FeNi_7	800
TP_44	FeNi_7	900
TP_50	FeNi_8	700
TP_51	FeNi_8	800
TP_52	FeNi_8	900
TP_80	FeNi_10	700
TP_81	FeNi_10	800
TP_82	FeNi_10	900
TP_83		
TP_84		
TP_85		
TP_86		

Figure 1: Image of the powders TP42 – TP86

2. Carbon-based thick films and their functional characterisation

The C-based thick films were prepared on alumina substrates by screen printing and subsequent firing at elevated temperatures. The suspension for screen printing was prepared from powders after pyrolysis. Powders were dispersed in an organic vehicle and then homogenized on a three-roll mill. The pastes were screen-printed in 8 mm × 8 mm square patterns on an alumina substrate (96% Al₂O₃) using a screen printer (P-250AVF, KEKO Equipment, Žužemberk, Slovenia). The deposits were dried at 150 °C for 15 minutes in air and then fired at 850 °C in an argon atmosphere. An image of the typical structure is shown in Figure 2a.

For electrochemical measurements, electrical connections were made from a silver paste, which was screen printed and fired at 1100 °C in air, and before electrochemical measurements, covered with a water-protective layer. The test structures were square-shaped, with dimensions of 8 mm.

Figure 2: Image of the a) square-shaped C-based thick film on alumina substrate, and b) electrochemical test structure with carbon-based WE and platinum electrical interconnections

The images show that thick films on alumina can be produced from carbon powders obtained after pyrolysis, confirming milestone M 4.1: Carbon powders suitable for thick film, and deliverable D 4.1: Carbon-based thick films on Al_2O_3 (demonstrator).

The test structures, obtained from different powders, were characterized by cyclic voltammetry using a potentiostat/galvanostat (Multi Autolab M 204, Metrohm, The Netherlands) with Nova 2.1.5 software. Measurements were performed at 25 °C in a 50 mL cell consisting of the test structure as the working electrode (WE), an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (RE), and a platinum sheet counter electrode.

Phosphate buffer solution (PBS) and hexacyanoferrate (II)/(III) solution (HCF) were prepared using ultrapure water (resistivity 18 M Ω ·cm). PBS with pH 7 was prepared from NaH₂PO₄ (99.0 %) and Na₂HPO₄ (Na₂HPO₄, >99.0 %). 1 mM hexacyanoferrate (II)/(III) solution (HCF) in PBS was prepared from K₄[Fe(CN)₆]·3H₂O (98.5 %) and K₃[Fe(CN)₆] (99 %). All CVs were recorded in PBS over a potential range from -0.2 V to +0.6 V, starting from an initial potential of 0.0 V in the positive direction, with a step potential of 2.44 mV. Three consecutive scans were recorded at a scan rate of 100 mV/s. Afterwards, the CVs were recorded in 1 mM HCF solution using the same procedure. The voltametric response of selected C-powders, measured in PBS and HCF, is shown in Figures 3–5.

Figure 3: Electrochemical response of TP42, TP43 and TP44 in PBS (dotted lines) and HCF (solid lines)

Figure 4: Electrochemical response of TP50, TP51 and TP52 in PBS (dotted lines) and HCF (solid lines)

Figure 5: Electrochemical response of TP80, TP81 and TP82 in PBS (dotted lines) and HCF (solid lines)

These results demonstrate that the thick films on alumina can be used as working electrodes for electrochemical measurements, confirming milestones M4.2: Electrochemical test structure fabricated, and M4.3: Electrochemical response of WE confirmed, as well as deliverable D4.2: Electrochemical test structure (demonstrator)

3. Integrated electrochemical sensor

JSI designed the electrochemical sensor test structure (ETS). The structure consists of working (WE), counter (CE), and reference (RE) electrodes, as well as electrical contacts, all integrated on an alumina substrate. The CE and electrical contacts were prepared from commercial platinum paste, which was deposited onto the alumina substrate by screen printing. The printed layers were fired at 1000 °C for 1 hour in air. The WE, made from carbon powders, was spherically shaped with a diameter of 4 mm. After screen printing, the carbon-thick films were fired at 850 °C for 30 minutes in argon. The Ag/AgCl reference electrode was screen printed and dried at 80 °C. The electrical contacts of the prepared samples were covered with a water-protective layer. The prepared ETS and the scheme for the electrochemical measurements are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively.

Figure 6: Fabricated electrochemical sensor test structure.

a)

b)

Figure 7: a) Scheme of electrochemical measurements, and b) experimental setup.

These results demonstrate that the electrochemical sensor test structure was fabricated, confirming milestone M4.2: Electrochemical test structure fabricated, and deliverable D4.2: Electrochemical test structure (demonstrator).

4. Characterisation of WE in model pesticide imidacloprid

The CVs in a model solution of the pesticide imidacloprid (IMD, $C_9H_{10}ClN_5O_2$, $\geq 98.0\%$, 0.1 mmol/L) in PBS with a carbon by-product-derived working electrode (WE) were recorded between -1.5 V and $+0.35$ V, starting from an initial potential of -0.2 V in the positive direction, at a scan rate of 100 mV s $^{-1}$. The CV was recorded after 3 minutes of accumulation under stirring conditions.

The voltametric response of TP 42, TP 43, and TP 44 measured in 0.1 mM imidacloprid is shown in Figure 8. A cathodic peak (I_{pc}) is characteristic of the irreversible reduction of the $-NO_2$ to $-NHOH$ functional group. As clearly shown in Figure 8, TP 42 and TP 43 exhibit this peak at potentials of -1.276 V and -1.166 V, respectively, both vs. Ag/AgCl, while the response of TP 44 is negligible. These results demonstrate that thick film structures prepared from carbon powders originating from the pyrolysis reaction are electrochemically active in model solutions of the pesticide imidacloprid. These powders, a by product of hydrogen production, can be used to fabricate miniature electrochemical sensors for detecting hazardous substances with redox-active nitro functional groups, such as neonicotinoid pesticides.

Figure 8: Voltametric response of TP 42, TP 43 and TP 44 measured in IMD

These results confirm the electrochemical response of the electrochemical test structure in the targeted analyte, the pesticide imidacloprid, as discussed and confirmed in this deliverable, D 4.3: Report on the electrochemical response of the electrochemical test structure (report).